

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Promotional influence, price, and product quality on the purchase decision of skincare products e-commerce in Indonesia

Khoirul Fuuad*, Reni Shinta Dewi and Hari Susanta Nugraha

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Social Science and Political Science, Universitas Diponegoro, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 24(02), 108-122

Publication history: Received on 22 September 2024; revised on 04 November 2024; accepted on 06 November 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.24.2.3197>

Abstract

This study aims to determine the influence of promotion, price, and product quality partially or simultaneously on the purchase decision of Whitelab Skincare Sunscreen products. The population in this study is consumers of Whitelab Skincare Sunscreen products in Jakarta. The number of samples of 100 respondents used a non-random sampling technique with the purposive sampling method. Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire. The analysis method used in this study is multiple linear regression analysis with the help of the SPSS version 25.00 program. Testing the partial hypothesis using the T test and simultaneously using the F test. The results showed that partial promotion, price, and product quality had a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision of Whitelab Skincare Sunscreen products.

Keywords: Promotion; Price; Quality of Product; Purchase Decision

1. Introduction

The current digital era, E-commerce has become one of the main channels for consumers to make purchases. The purchasing decision-making process in e-commerce involves a variety of complex factors. Starting from information search to product alternative evaluation. The main factors influencing purchase decisions in e-commerce include consumer trust in the platform, product information quality, price, and user experience. There are many options available, consumers tend to do more in-depth research before making a final decision. Moreover, reviews and recommendations from other users also play an important role in shaping consumer perception and trust. In this context, understanding consumer behavior and the factors that influence purchasing decisions is crucial for e-commerce players in designing effective marketing strategies. Through this understanding, businesses can improve the user experience, building trust, and ultimately drive sales conversions. This introduction will discuss more about the dynamics of purchasing decisions in e-commerce and the factors that influence them.

In Indonesia, the development of e-commerce is relatively fast, even Indonesia is among the countries with the largest number of e-commerce transactions in Southeast Asia. The high growth of e-commerce causes entrepreneurs to start marketing their markets through certain existing platforms because online market buying and selling transactions such as market places that have been widely used today there are several that are often used by marketplaces that are often used by consumers in Indonesia, namely Tokopedia, Shopee, Lazada and various other types of shopping platforms. For this reason, the development of the e-commerce concept has resulted in the emergence of many businesses that can increase the growth of their economic stability.

Based on e-commerce visitor report data. The largest number of e-commerce site visits in Indonesia in the 1st to 4th quarters of 2023, namely Shopee with the number of visitors in the first quarter of 158 million to 242 million in the fourth quarter, placing it in first place. Tokopedia ranks second with an average number of visitors, which is 105 million

* Corresponding author: Khoirul Fuuad

visitors. The last position is occupied by Bukalapak with an average number of visitors of 14 million visitors throughout 2023. The following is a report on e-commerce visitor data to the 5 largest sites in Indonesia in 2023.

Table 1 Report e-commerce visitors

E-commerce	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Shopee	157,966,666	166,966,666	216,766,666	241,600,000
Tokopedia	117,033,333	107,200,000	97,066,666	96,933,333
Loop	83,233,333	74,533,333	52,233,333	44,133,333
Blibli	25,433,333	27,100,000	28,400,000	31,533,333
Bukalapak	18,066,666	15,566,666	12,366,666	10,066,666

Source : Katadata.co.id

In 2023, the data of visitors to e-commerce shopping platforms in Indonesia shows an encouraging trend. Here are some key points that reflect the situation:

- Number of Visitors

Large e-commerce platforms such as Tokopedia, Shopee, and Bukalapak recorded hundreds of millions of monthly visits with Shopee often in the top position.

- Active Users

It is estimated that there are more than 100 million active e-commerce users in Indonesia, with many shopping regularly.

- Visitor Demographics

Most of the visitors are the younger generation (Millennials and Gen Z), who are more accustomed to shopping online.

- Traffic Increase at Certain Times

Such as during shopping festivals (for example. Flash sale or 11.11), Traffic is increasing rapidly with a significant surge in transactions.

- Devices Used

Most visitors access the platform through mobile devices. shows that mobile applications are increasingly dominant in shopping behavior.

- Purchasing Tendency

The most in-demand categories include fashion. electronic. and daily needs.

The skincare industry has undergone a significant transformation in recent years. Especially with the emergence of e-commerce as the main channel for product sales. The rapid growth of digital technology and increased internet access have changed the way consumers interact with skincare brands and products. E-commerce offers convenience for consumers to explore a wide range of products, read reviews, and compare prices without geographical restrictions. In Indonesia. This phenomenon is very visible, with many e-commerce platforms that offer skincare products from various local and international brands.

Consumers are now more likely to do online research before making a purchase, often relying on influencer recommendations or user reviews. This triggers brands to focus more on digital marketing and product development that suits consumer needs. The availability of abundant information and ease of making purchases make e-commerce the main choice for many people who want to take care of their skin, with a variety of products that continue to grow.

E-commerce is not just a market, but also an educational platform about effective skin care. The skincare industry in e-commerce is predicted to continue to grow in line with the increasing awareness of skin care and the increasingly diverse needs of consumers.

Table 2 Best Selling Skincare Brands in Ecommerce in 2022

Brand of Skincare	Revenue (in billions)
Somethinc	53.2
Scarlett	40.9
Ms.Glow	29.4
Avoskin	28.0
Whitelab	25.3

Source : compass.co.id

The data is based on the 5 best-selling Indonesian local brands sold in e-commerce in 2022. In first position, Somethinc achieved the largest sales of IDR 53.2 billion throughout 2022. Although the brand is among the youngest local brands because the brand was established in 2019. Somethinc offers products that have been tailored to overcome Indonesian women's skin problems with high-quality ingredients.

The second favorite local skincare brand is Scarlett. This brand is a body care product brand from Indonesia and is famous for its series of whitening products. Total sales for the Scarlett brand itself have exceeded IDR 40.9 billion in the 2022 period. The Scarlett brand has released several series of skincare products that are favourites such as body lotion, body scrub, and also shampoo. One of the favorite products, namely Scarlett Whitening Acne Serum.

This local skincare brand, which was established in 2013, managed to occupy the first position with total sales that managed to reach IDR 29.4 billion in the 2022 period. The MS Glow brand has a series of brightening skincare products that are formulated effectively to treat and brighten dull skin. MS Glow also does not only focus on developing treatment products for women, but also men by presenting their flagship products namely MS Glow Men Skincare.

This local skincare brand is one of the brands under the auspices of PT AVO Innovation Technology. The Avoskin brand began to emerge in 2014 and continues to grow on this day. Avoskin managed to occupy the fourth position with total sales of IDR 28 billion, famous for using a green beauty concept. The skincare products of this brand consistently use good and gentle ingredients from nature such as tea tree, aloe vera, and raspberries. So, don't be surprised if Avoskin is one of the mainstay skincare brands to overcome various sensitive skin problems.

The brand that has just emerged, namely Whitelab in March 2020, managed to enter the top 5 rankings for local skincare brands. The sales can also be said to be quite good because in the 2022 period it has been able to reach a total of IDR 25.3 billion. Facial care products and body care products are the two big categories that Whitelab offers. As for the best-selling product, after exploring more deeply, it turns out that the Whitelab Brightening Face Serum.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1 Promotion

Warren & Keegan (2017) states that promotion refers to a consumer communication or sales program that is paid for a limited duration that adds real value to a product or brand. Meanwhile, according to Kotler & Armstrong (2018), sales promotion is the shortest short-term promotional mix tool. Sales promotions provide short-term incentives to encourage the purchase or sale of products or services. According to Zahara & Sembiring (2020), promotion is an activity to provide information to the public about the products that will be offered so that consumers are interested in buying the products or services offered. According to Hadibrata et al (2017), promotion is defined as a form of marketing communication is a marketing activity that seeks to disseminate information, influence/persuade consumers in choosing their products to be willing to accept, buy, and loyal to the products offered by the company concerned. It can be concluded that promotional activities are communication activities between buyers and sellers regarding the existence of products or services to convince and refine the product or service so that it can influence attitudes and

behaviors that encourage communication and marketing activities. Promotion in this study was measured by an indicator: advertising, sales promotion, direct marketing, and word of mouth (Kotler & Keller. 2016).

2.1.2 Price

Warren & Keegan (2017), states that price can be used as a strategic variable to achieve a specific financial goal, including return on investment and recovery of product development costs. Meanwhile, according to Kotler & Armstrong (2018), price is the amount of money charged for a product or service, or the amount of value that a customer redeems for the benefit of owning or using the product or service. In the narrowest sense, price is the amount of money charged for a product or service. According to Nasution et al. (2020), price is something that means a lot to consumers and sellers. For consumers, price is the cost of something. As for sellers, price is one of the sources of income or profit. It can be concluded that price is one of the determining factors for buyers to determine the decision to purchase products or services. The price in this study is measured by an indicator, affordable price, price compatibility with product quality, discounts, and price competitiveness (Kotler & Armstrong. 2018).

2.1.3 Product Quality

According to (Kotler and Armstrong, 2018), quality is the characteristic of a product in its ability to meet predetermined and latent needs. According to (Kotler and Armstrong, 2018), which states that product quality is the ability of a product to demonstrate its function. In this case, it includes overall durability, reliability, accuracy, ease of operation, and product repair, also other product attributes. If a product can carry out its function, the product can be said to have good quality. According to (Assauri. 2009) things that can directly affect product quality are called the Nine basic areas or 9M namely: market, money, management, man (human), motivation, material, machine and meccanization, modern information method and mounting product requirement.

2.1.4 Purchase Decision

Swastha and Handoko (2011) stated that there are five roles of individuals in a buying decision, that is:

- Initiator: individuals who have the initiative to purchase certain goods or who have needs or desires but do not have the authority to do it themselves.
- Influencers: individuals who influence the decision to buy either intentionally or unintentionally.
- Decision-makers (decider): individuals who decide whether to buy or not, what to buy, how to buy it, when and where to buy it.
- Buyer: the individual who makes the actual purchase.
- User: an individual who enjoys or uses the purchased product or service.

2.2. Methods

This study uses two method approaches that can be used, namely quantitative research and basic research with the aim of analyzing problems that occur in a formation and finding ways to solve certain problems so that in this study. Basic research is conducted to understand the factors that influence purchase decisions and identify the relationship between promotions, price, and product quality. Therefore, this study uses a basic research approach to understand a problem and find a solution as well as a quantitative research approach to conduct a survey technique to analyses the relationship between variables by collecting data through the questionnaire that has been distributed, this will make a more comprehensive understanding of the influence of purchase decisions on promotions, price, and product quality, related to the use of skincare in the city of Jakarta.

In the study of Sugiyono (2020), the criteria for e-commerce users domiciled in the city of Jakarta in this study are needed primary data and secondary sources as used for the data collection process.

2.2.1 Population and Sample

Population according to Sugiyono (2020) is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics that are determined by the researcher to be studied and then drawn conclusions. The population in this study is all Sunscreen skincare users in the city of Jakarta.

The sample used in this study was 100 respondents using the formula from Slovin. et.al (Ridwan, 2010) with an unknown population, with the determination of the sample used, that is:

$$n = (0,25) \left(\frac{Z\alpha/2}{e} \right)^2$$

$$n = (0,25) \left(\frac{1,96}{0,1} \right)^2$$

$$n = (0,25)(384,16)$$

$$n = 96,04 \rightarrow 100$$

Information:

n	=	Number of samples (made by respondents)
Z $\alpha/2$	=	Standard grades. Normal distribution for the set confidence interval (0.05/2=0.025 → See table Z = 1.96)
e	=	Error sampling (acceptable estimate)

The sampling technique used in this study is nonprobability sampling which is a sampling technique that does not provide an opportunity for each member of the population to be used as a sample member (Ridwan, 2010). Meanwhile, the method used is Purposive Random Sampling, which is a sampling technique used by researchers if the researcher has certain considerations in considering the sample for a certain purpose (Ridwan, 2010).

2.2.2 Data collection techniques

- Questionnaire

According to Sugiyono (2020), questionnaires are data collection techniques that are carried out by giving a set of questions or written statements to respondents to answer. The questionnaires distributed were measured by the Likert scale. The Likert scale is used to measure the attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. The variables measured are described as variable indicators. Then it is used as a starting point to compile items that can be in the form of statements or questions.

In this method, the author uses an interval Likert scale where the answers consist of: strongly agree, agree, quite agree, disagree, strongly disagree.

- Literature review

That is study literature, magazines and notes related to the problems discussed in order to obtain a theoretical framework as well as a basic framework and analysis tool. This is intended as a reference source to discuss the theory underlying the discussion of the problem in this study. To complete the information. The researcher also cited several articles accessed on various sites on the internet.

2.2.3 Operational Definition of Variables

This study uses two types of variables, namely independent variables and dependent variables. The Independent Variable (Independent Variable) in this study is promotion, price, and product quality. The Dependent Variable (Bound Variable) in this study is the purchase decision. Variable operation is a definition given to a variable by giving meaning or specifying an activity or justifying an operation necessary to measure the variable (Sugiyono, 2020).

Table 3 Operational Definition of Variables

Variable	Operational Definition	Indicator
Promotion (X1)	Promotion is an activity that communicates the advantages of a product and persuades customers to buy the product (Kotler and Armstrong. 2014).	1) Promotion frequency. 2) Quality promotion. 3) Promotion quantity. 4) Promotion timing. 5) Accuracy of promotion.
Price (x2)	Price is the amount of money exchanged for a product and service (Kotler and Armstrong. 2014).	1) Affordability. 2) Price competitiveness. 3) Suitability of price with product quality. 4) Discounts. 5) Suitability of price with benefits.
Product Quality (x3)	Product quality is a consumer assessment of the excellence or privilege of a product (Tjiptono. 2008).	1) Performance. 2) Durability. 3) Specification conformity. 4) Additional privileges. 5) Reliability. 6) Aesthetics.
Purchase Decision (Y)	Purchase decisions are stages made by consumers before making a decision to buy a product (Kotler. 2009).	1) Recognition of needs. 2) Information search. 3) Alternative assessment. 4) Purchase decision. 5) Post-purchase behavior.

Source: Data processed by the author, 2024.

2.2.4 Data Processing and Analysis Techniques

The research instrument used in this study is a questionnaire/questionnaire containing questions. Moreover, the instrument used by this study is documentation. The instrument tests in this study are validity tests and reliability tests with the help of the SPSS program version 25.00.

- Descriptive Analysis

The author used descriptive analysis to find out the characteristics of the respondents in this study.

- Classical Assumption Test

The data was processed using the help of the SPSS version 25.00 program with the regression method if the classical assumption test was met. If the classical assumption is not fulfilled then use non-parametric statistics, classical assumption tests are like normality tests, multicollinearity test, and heteroscedasticity test.

- Hypothesis Test

The hypothesis test in this study uses Multiple Liner Regression Analysis, Test t (Partial Test), Test F (Simultaneous Test), and Coefficient of Determination. The equation for multiple linear regression analysis is as follows:

$$Y=b_1X_1+b_2X_2+b_3X_3$$

Where:

- Y = Purchase Decision
- X1 = Promotion
- X2 = Price
- X3 = Product Quality
- b1, b2, b3 = Regression coefficient

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Data Analysis

3.1.1 Validity Test

Data analysis from Promotions (X1)

Table 4 Data analysis from Promotions (X1)

No	Indicator	Calculate	>/<	Table	Results
1	X1.1	0.704	>	0.165	Valid
2	X1.2	0.671	>	0.165	Valid
3	X1.3	0.712	>	0.165	Valid
4	X1.4	0.792	>	0.165	Valid
5	X1.5	0.804	>	0.165	Valid
6	X1.6	0.687	>	0.165	Valid
7	X1.7	0.728	>	0.165	Valid
8	X1.8	0.633	>	0.165	Valid
9	X1.9	0.652	>	0.165	Valid
10	X1.10	0.775	>	0.165	Valid

Source: Data processed by the author, 2024.

Data from Price (x2)

Table 5 Data analysis of Price (X2)

No	Indicator	Calculate	>/<	Table	Results
1	X2.1	0.650	>	0.165	Valid
2	X2.2	0.640	>	0.165	Valid
3	X2.3	0.724	>	0.165	Valid
4	X2.4	0.734	>	0.165	Valid
5	X2.5	0.777	>	0.165	Valid
6	X2.6	0.788	>	0.165	Valid
7	X2.7	0.815	>	0.165	Valid
8	X2.8	0.696	>	0.165	Valid
9	X2.9	0.701	>	0.165	Valid
10	X2.10	0.605	>	0.165	Valid

Source: Data processed by the author, 2024.

Data from Product Quality (x3)

Table 6 Data analysis of Product Quality (X3)

No	Indicator	Calculate	>/<	Table	Results
1	X3.1	0.824	>	0.165	Valid
2	X3.2	0.787	>	0.165	Valid
3	X3.3	0.791	>	0.165	Valid
4	X3.4	0.877	>	0.165	Valid
5	X3.5	0.856	>	0.165	Valid
6	X3.6	0.742	>	0.165	Valid
7	X3.7	0.844	>	0.165	Valid
8	X3.8	0.756	>	0.165	Valid
9	X3.9	0.744	>	0.165	Valid
10	X310	0.743	>	0.165	Valid

Source: Data processed by the author, 2024.

Data from Purchase Decision (Y)

Table 7 Data analysis from Purchase Decision (Y)

No	Indicator	Calculate	>/<	Table	Results
1	Y.1	0.583	>	0.165	Valid
2	Y.2	0.800	>	0.165	Valid
3	Y.3	0.738	>	0.165	Valid
4	Y.4	0.768	>	0.165	Valid
5	Y.5	0.744	>	0.165	Valid
6	Y.6	0.714	>	0.165	Valid
7	Y.7	0.770	>	0.165	Valid
8	Y.8	0.666	>	0.165	Valid

Source: Data processed by the author, 2024.

3.1.2 Reliability Test

The reliability test of the instrument uses a test with a significance level of 5%. If the R alpha > 0.60, the instrument is declared reliable. The calculation of this reliability analysis uses SPSS 25.0 software.

The following are the results of reliability tests on the four research variables.

Table 8 Questionnaire Reliability Test Results

Variable	Ralph	Information
Promotion (X1)	0.894	Reliable
Price (x2)	0.893	Reliable
Product Quality (x3)	0.895	Reliable
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.869	Reliable

Source: Data processed by the author, 2024.

3.2. Analysis Description

In this study, a questionnaire was distributed to 100 respondents to users of Whitelab Sunscreen skincare products in Jakarta. An overview of the characteristics of the respondents was obtained from the personal data contained in the respondent's identity data section which included age, purchase volume, and the frequency of use.

3.2.1 Description of Respondent Characteristics by Age

Respondent characteristics based on age category can be presented in Figure 1 of the total 100 respondents of Whitelab Sunscreen skincare consumers who were sampled in this study. The majority are 21-25 years old, which is 48%. Then the age of 17-20 years is 35% and the age over 25 years is 17%.

Figure 1 Characteristics of Respondents by Age

3.2.2 Characteristics of Respondents Based on Frequency of Use

The characteristics of respondents based on the frequency of use of Whitelab Skincare sunscreen can be presented in Figure 2. The data shows that out of a total of 100 respondents used in this study, the most respondents rarely use Whitelab Skincare sunscreen, which is 56% and the rest often use as much as 44%.

Figure 2. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Frequency of Use

3.3. Statistical Analysis

3.3.1 Classical Assumption Test

A good regression model must be free of the problem of deviation from classical assumptions.

The following is a test against the classical assumptions in the regression model:

- Normality Test

The normality test was carried out through a non-parametric statistical test of Kolmogorov – Smirnov (K-S) with the hypothesis:

- H0 : Normally distributed residual data
- H1 : Residual data is not normally distributed

H0 is accepted if the significance value is greater than 0.05, while H0 is rejected if the significance value is less than 0.05.

The test results are in the following Table 8:

Table 9 Validity Test with One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0E-7
	Std. Deviation	3.36904593
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0.078
	Positive	0.055
	Negative	-0.078
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		0.777
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		0.581
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		

Source : Primary data (processed by the author, 2024)

From Table 9 above, the significance value of *Kolmogorov – Smirnov* is obtained of 0.581, since the significance level > 0.05, H0 or residual data is normally distributed.

- Multicollinearities Test

A variable showing symptoms of multicollinearity can be seen from the high value of VIF (*Variance Inflation Factor*) in the independent variables of a regression model. A VIF value greater than 10 indicates the presence of symptoms of multicollinearity in the regression model. The results of the multicollinearity test with VIF values are as follows:

Table 10 Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients			
Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
	Promotion	0.355	2.817
	Price	0.355	2.817
	Product Quality	0.355	2.817

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source : Primary data (Processed by the author, 2024)

The test results show that all the variables used as predictors of the regression model show a fairly small VIF value, where all of them are below 10 and the tolerance value is more than 0.10. This means that the independent variables used in the study did not show any symptoms of multicollinearity, which means that all of these variables can be used as variables that are independent of each other.

- Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity occurs when there is no similarity in the standard deviation of the value of the dependent variable in each independent variable.

Table 11 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Coefficient						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	1.734	2.381		.728	.468
1	X1	0.014	0.076	0.019	0.182	0.856
	X2	-0.008	0.059	-0.015	-0.140	0.889
	X3	0.005	0.050	0.010	0.093	0.926

Source : Primary data (Processed by the author, 2024)

- Multiple Regression Analysis

Changes in the value of a variable do not always occur by themselves. However, changes in the value of the variable can also be caused by changes in other variables related to that variable to find out the pattern of changes in the value of the buying interest variable caused by promotion, price, and quality of products variable an analysis tool is needed that allows us to make an estimate or forecast the value of the variable on a certain value of the variable that affects it.

The multiple linear regression analysis in this study uses the SPSS program and can be seen in the table below:

Table 12 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Coefficients				
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients
		B	Std. Error	Beta
1	(Constant)	4.860	2.268	
	Promotion	0.210	0.089	0.262
	Price	0.280	0.087	0.241
	Product Quality	0.432	0.089	0.535

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision; ource : Primary data (Processed by the author, 2024)

Based on the results of data processing as seen in Table 11, the multiple regression equation is obtained as follows:

$$Y = a + \beta_{1X1} + \beta_{2X2} + \beta_{3X3}$$

$$Y = 4.860 + 0.210X1 + 0.280X2 + 0.432X3$$

The following is an explanation based on the multiple regression equation that is formed:

- The value of the regression coefficient in the promotion variable (X1) is 0.262, this shows that the promotional variable has a positive value so that if the promotional variable increases, the purchase decision will increase.
- The value of the regression coefficient in the price variable (X2) is 0.241, this shows that the price variable has a positive value so that if the price increases, the purchase decision will increase.
- The value of the regression coefficient in the product quality variable (X3) is 0.535, this shows that the product quality variable has a positive value so that if the product quality improves, the purchase decision will increase.
- **Hypothesis Testing**

Partial Test (t-Test)

The t-test is used to determine the partial influence of independent variables (price, promotion, and product quality) on dependent variables (purchase decisions). The following will explain the partial testing of each variable.

Table 13 Test Results t

Variable	Calculation	Sig.	T table	Results
Promotion	2.013	0.047	1.984	H1 accepted
Price	3.231	0.002	1.984	H2 accepted
Product Quality	7.717	0.000	1.984	H3 accepted

Source : Primary data (Processed by the author, 2024)

- The promotion variable in table 13 can be known as a coefficient value of 0.224 and t calculated as 2.013. If the t count is compared to the t table, then $2.013 > 1.984$ which means that the t count is greater than the t table, and significance values of $0.047 < 0.05$. This shows that the promotion variable has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision. (H1 accepted).
- The price variable in table 13 can be known to have a coefficient value of 0.280 and t calculated as $3.231 > 1.984$ which means t calculated is greater than t table and the significance value is $0.002 < 0.05$, this shows that price variables have a positive and significant effect on purchase decisions. (H2 accepted).
- The product quality variable in table 13 can be known to have a coefficient value of 0.563 and t calculated as $7.717 > 1.984$ which means that t is greater than t table and the significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that the product quality variable has a positive and significant effect on the purchase decision. (H3 accepted).

Simultaneous Test (Test F)

To test whether price, promotion, and product quality can actually be used to predict Y, the F test will be used.

Table 14 Test Result F

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Mr.
	Regression	707.423	3	235.808	31.523	0.000b
1	Residuals	718.137	96	7.481		
	Total	1425.560	99			

Source : Primary data (Processed by the author, 2024)

Based on table 14, It can be seen that the probability value in this study is 0.000 which means that this number is below 0.05 and the F calculation is 31.523, when compared to the F table then $31,523 > 2,700$ which means that the F calculation is greater than the F table. The conclusion that can be drawn is the promotion variable, price, and product quality simultaneously (together) affect the purchase decision. (H4 accepted).

- **Coefficient of Determination (R²)**

The determination coefficient is used to find out how much the influence of the independent variable has an effect on the bound variable. The value of the determination coefficient is determined by the value of the adjusted R square as can be seen in Table 15.

Table 15 Determination Testing

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.704a	0.496	0.481	2.735
a. Predictors: (Constant). Promotion. Price. and Product Quality				
b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision				

Source : Primary data (Processed by the author, 2024)

Based on table 15, it is known that the value of the determination coefficient (Adjusted R Square) is obtained as 0.481 or 48.1%, this means that 48.1% of the variation in purchase decisions is influenced by promotional variables, price, and product quality while the remaining 51.9% was influenced by other variables that were not used in this study.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Effect of Promotions on Purchase Decisions

The results of the statistical calculation on the promotion variable obtained a regression coefficient of 0.210 which means that the promotion variable has a positive influence. This means that if the promotion increases, the buying interest by consumers in Whitelab skincare sunscreen will increase. Meanwhile, the level of significance of the study on the promotion variable was obtained as $0.047 < 0.05$. This study is also supported by the opinion (Kotler and Armstrong, 2018) which states that promotion is an activity that communicates the advantages of the product and persuades buyers to be willing to buy the product. Therefore, Whitelab should continue to increase the type of promotions carried out in order to increase the number of sales transactions every month. Based on the results of the analysis above, it can be concluded that H1 in this study is accepted.

4.2. The Effect of Price on Purchase Decisions

Based on the t. test, the results of the price variable in table 13 can be found to have a significance value of 0.002 and a calculated t of 3.231. If the t calculation is compared to the t table, then $3.231 > 1.984$ which means that the t calculation

is greater than the t table. and a significance value of $0.002 < 0.05$, this shows that price variables have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions on skincare sunscreen products.

The result of this study is that purchase decisions can be influenced by price, this is in accordance with the hypothesis that was built earlier. The results of this study are in line with previous research that price has a significant effect on purchasing decisions at Billionaire Store Bandung (Kambali & Syarifah, 2020). Likewise, other studies show that price has a significant effect on purchasing decisions (Gunarsih & Tamengkel, 2021).

4.3. The Effect of Product Quality on Purchase Decisions

The results of statistical calculations on the product quality variable obtained a regression coefficient of 0.432 which means that the product quality variable has a positive influence. This means that if the product quality variable is increasing. then the purchase decision from consumers for Whitelab Skincare Sunscreen will also increase. Likewise, vice versa if product quality decreases. then buying interest will also decrease.

Meanwhile, the level of significance of the study on the product quality variable was obtained as $0.000 < 0.05$, Whitelab Skincare Sunscreen has product quality with good results in increasing protection on the face so as to arouse interest and increase consumer buying interest in Skincare Sunscreen.

The findings of this study are in accordance with previous research by Andi et al. (2020) which in their research also proved that product quality affects buying interest. Similarly, in the research of Maulida et al. (2019) who prove that product quality affects consumer buying interest.

4.4. Promotional Influence. Price. Product Quality to Purchase Decisions

Based on the F test in table 14, it can be known that the significance value is 0.000 which means that this number is below 0.05 and the F calculation is 31.523, when compared to the F table then $31,523 > 2,700$ which means that the F calculation is greater than the F table. The conclusion that can be drawn is the promotion variable. price. and product quality simultaneously (together) affects the purchase decision on Whitelab Sunscreen skincare products. Based on the results of the analysis above, it can be concluded that H4 in this study is accepted.

5. Conclusion

This study aims to find out this research which was held to research the influence of promotion, price, and product quality which acts as an independent variable and purchase decision which is a dependent variable of skincare products in e-commerce. So the company must be able to improve these three factors that can affect the purchase decision.

For the next researcher, it would be good to expand the observed variables. Researchers can then add variables that are in line that can further strengthen the existing discussion with various aspects in it.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflicts of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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